

1. Electron micrograph shows virus particles in phloem cell of a rice plant infected with ragged stunt disease in Thailand.

Inoculation of from 15 to 20 healthy plants with 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 viruliferous insects/seedling resulted in 15, 20, 13, 47, and 61% infected plants, respectively.

Healthy insects were confined on diseased plants for acquisition feeding for 0, 0.5, 1, 3, 6, 24, and 48 hours. The insects were then used to inoculate from

15 to 19 seedlings at 5 insects/seedling for 24 hours. Infection for the 7 feeding periods was 0, 0, 0, 13, 11, 16, and 22% of the plants, respectively, indicating that 3 hours was the shortest time required for the insect to acquire the virus.

Five viruliferous insects per plant were

used to inoculate sets of from 17 to 22 healthy plants, for periods of 0, 0.5, 1, 3, 6, and 24 hours. Infection was 0, 0, 5, 18, 39, and 25%, respectively, indicating that the shortest time required for insects to successfully inoculate a plant was 1 hour.

Photo 2 shows symptoms of artificially infected TN1 plants.

2. TN1 plants that were successfully infected with ragged stunt disease showed typical symptoms: ragged and twisted leaves.

Pest management and control

INSECTS

Use of multihole vinyl tube to dust insecticides for brown planthopper control

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During massive and extensive outbreaks of brown planthoppers (BPH), conventional insecticide treatments are often ineffective. Some major factors that contribute to such ineffectiveness are the failure to cover the entire affected area lapidly and simultaneously, and the

incomplete penetration into the plant bases. Application systems that could overcome such limitations would undoubtedly be advantageous. Therefore, dusting from a multihole vinyl tube was evaluated using approximately 33.6 kg Sogatox[®] (2% MTMC:2% phenthoate) of dust/ha. Basically, the system consists of a Maruyama Knapsack Power Mist Duster that drives the insecticidal dust over the plants through regularly spaced openings on the underside of a long vinyl tube (see photo).

Two trials were conducted: the first at dusk over 1.5 ha in Parit 3 (Sg. Burong), and the second at dawn over 3 ha in Parit 4 (Sg. Burong). In both treated fields the rice variety was Mat Candu. Just before and periodically after

treatment (at 2 months after transplanting), populations of BPH and of the common predators on 50 random hills from each field were determined. Parallel counts were made in two untreated fields.

Except in the controls, BPH mortality was 100% within 1.5 to 2 hours after dusting (see table). However, first-instar nymphs emerged 2 days after treatments and increased rapidly, suggesting that BPH eggs already present were not affected, and that the treatments had little residual effects. More than one treatment was necessary to ensure effective control.

Such limitations may have contributed to the numerous past unsuccessful attempts to control large-scale BPH

outbreaks with chemicals. Besides causing a sharp decline in the infesting BPH populations, the treatments also adversely affected such common predators as *Casnoidea interstitialis*, *Coccinella arcuata*, *Orthorhinus lividipennis*, and *Paederus fuscipes* (see table). The population of these predators, however, gradually built up again.

Although it has limitations, the tube dusting system appears to possess several advantages over most other methods in ground application of insecticides: 1) handling is relatively simple and easy — only two persons are needed to operate it; 2) neither water nor mixing of insecticides is needed; 3) extensive areas can be rapidly treated — only 15–20 minutes is necessary to cover 0.4 ha; 4) the treatment is uniform and thorough, and penetration is good; and 5) BPH suppression is rapid and highly effective. As these advantages constitute some of the basic operational features desired of chemical control, the tube dusting system would thus play a major role in combatting BPH infestations, especially during outbreaks. **W**

Use of the multi-hole vinyl tube to dust insecticides against brown planthoppers. Sg. Burong, Malaysia.

Effects of Sogatox[®] (2% MTMC:2% phenthoate) at 33.6 kg formulated dust/ha on the rice brown planthopper and its common predators. Sg. Burong, Malaysia, 1978.

Date	BPH and predator populations (no./50 hills)									
	Treated ^a					Control ^a				
	BPH	CI	Ca	Pf	Ci	BPH	CI	Ca	Pf	Ci
<i>Trial 1</i>										
Pretreatment count										
21 Jan.	552	14	2	8	0	552	14	2	8	0
Posttreatment count										
2 h later	0	0	0	0	0	309	68	1	1	4
1 Feb	0	0	0	0	0	608	36	1	1	0
2 Feb	34 ^b	0	0	0	0	—	—	—	—	—
3 Feb	—	—	—	—	—	686	31	5	6	2
9 Feb	711 ^c	14	1	1	3	—	—	—	—	—
<i>Trial 2</i>										
Pretreatment count										
1 Feb	1,131	5	9	1	1	608	37	1	2	2
Posttreatment count										
1½ h later	0	0	0	0	0	—	—	—	—	—
2 Feb	0	0	0	0	0	—	—	—	—	—
3 Feb	56 ^b	0	0	1	0	602	54	1	0	1
9 Feb	711 ^c	3	0	0	1	—	—	—	—	—

^a BPH = brown planthopper, CI = *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis*, Ca = *Coccinella arcuata*, Pf = *Paederus fuscipes*, Ci = *Casnoidea interstitialis*.

^b First-instar nymphs.

^c Predominantly early instar nymphs.